

PARAMETERS INFLUENCING THE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF A CHOPPED CARBON FIBER / POLYMER COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the effect of the fiber length and concentration on the thermal conductivity of a chopped pitch-based carbon fiber/polymer composite is investigated. Samples of polycarbonate filled with different amounts of chopped carbon fibers with a given orientation were realized and measurements of thermal conductivity were performed in two perpendicular directions. A model based on an analogy with mechanical properties to account for the results is proposed. Very good agreement was found between data and the model. Finally, we show that, even with chopped fibers, thermal conductivities comparable to that of stainless steel can be readily attained.

Keywords : Thermal conductivity, composite, pitch-based carbon fiber, polycarbonate

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing needs for materials dedicated to thermal management applications has led to the design of new composite materials. Indeed, with appropriate combination of selected matrices and fillers, and the use of new processing techniques, it is now possible to tailor composite materials with almost the desired thermal conductivity. Thermoplastic polymers filled with chopped highly thermally conductive pitch-based carbon fibers are good candidates for such applications.

Up to now, most of the research works devoted to the study of thermal conductivity of composites were mainly concerned with fillers with small aspect ratios (1). As a consequence, very little is known about thermal conductivity of polymers loaded with elongated particles (2).

We have developed in our laboratory different processing techniques and measuring devices in order to investigate the effect of a series of parameters relative to either the fibers or the matrix on the thermal conductivity of such materials.

We propose to demonstrate here the strong influence of the fiber orientation and concentration on the thermal conductivity of a chopped carbon fibers/polymer composite. For this, samples of polycarbonate filled with different amounts of chopped carbon fibers with a given orientation have been realised. Then, measurements of thermal conductivity were performed in two perpendicular directions.

A model based on an analogy with mechanical properties is proposed and is shown to fit the results quite well.

Finally, we show that, even with chopped fibers, thermal conductivities comparable to that of stainless steel can be readily attained.

2. SAMPLES

The polymer we used was Polycarbonate Lexan™ 145 from GE Plastics. Its room temperature thermal conductivity is $0.2 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. The choice of the polymer was dictated by the fact that we wanted to avoid a matrix with different crystallinity degrees. Indeed, crystallinity degree may have a strong influence on the thermal conductivity of the polymer (3).

The fibers were P55 pitch-based carbon fibers from AMOCO. These fibers have a rather high room temperature thermal conductivity of $100 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ and an electrical resistivity of $10^{-5} \Omega\text{m}$ (4). For the purpose of this experiment, the fibers were cut manually by means of a series of razor blades strung on a rod and separated by 1 mm thick interleaves. This operation yielded fibers that were about 1 mm long.

2.1. Fabrication of the composites

A method for processing the composites was developed. This method may also be used for composites with any other kind of particles.

The method consists of freezing a mixture of chopped carbon fibers and polymer dissolved in a solvent. The solid solvent is then sublimated and the remaining porous material hot-pressed in plaques of $50 \times 50 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$. This last step gave rise to a strong orientation of the fibers that were roughly evenly dispersed in planes perpendicular to the pressing direction. The samples were then cut out of the plaques. A more detailed description of this fabrication technique is given elsewhere (5).

It is worth noting that some fibers broke during the processing of the composite, thus resulting in a small decrease of the average fiber length.

The fiber volume fraction (Vf) in the composites ranged from 0 to 30 volume percent.

3. TECHNIQUES OF MEASUREMENT

3.1 Out-of-Plane thermal conductivity

The out-of-plane thermal conductivity was measured at room temperature by means of a home-made system. This set-up, based on a modified version of the guarded hot-plate method (two probe technique), needs 3 mm thick and 32 mm in diameter disk-shaped samples. As the heat flux is perpendicular to the main faces of the plaques, it is also roughly perpendicular to the fibers in the composite.

A correction of the measured values was performed to take into account the thermal contact resistances between the sample and the set-up. Precision of the measured values is estimated around 10%.

A complete description of this set-up is given elsewhere (5).

3.2 In plane thermal conductivity

The principle used for the in-plane thermal conductivity measurement was based on the four probe technique. A description of this technique is given elsewhere (6).

4. RESULTS

4.1 Out-of-plane thermal conductivity

Results for the out-of-plane thermal conductivity dependence on the fiber volume fraction are reported in figure 1. A threefold increase in thermal conductivity is observed and its dependence on fiber volume fraction is linear.

4.2 In-plane-thermal conductivity

Results for the in-plane thermal conductivity dependence on the fiber volume fraction are reported in figure 2.

Unlike out-of-plane thermal conductivity, the dependence on the fiber concentration here is very large. Indeed, values as high as $10 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ can readily be attained. It is worth noting that this value is comparable to that of stainless steel. Furthermore, for fiber concentrations lower than 20%, the dependence on fiber volume fraction is linear.

Figure 1 : Out-of-plane thermal conductivity dependence on the fiber volume fraction

Figure 2 : In-plane thermal conductivity dependence on the fiber volume fraction

5. DISCUSSION

The comparison between these two series of measurements clearly highlights the strong effect of the fiber orientation on the thermal conductivity. Indeed, in the direction perpendicular to the fiber axis, only a very poor increase in thermal conductivity is observed compared with that in the in-plane direction. This can easily be explained by the fact that the out-of-plane heat flux only "sees" the diameter of the fiber while the in-plane heat flux "sees" the fiber length.

For concentrations lower than 20%, the dependence on the fiber concentration was linear in both series of measurements. The saturation observed above 20% fiber concentration for the in-plane thermal conductivity can be ascribed to the existence of a maximum in the packing that can be achieved for any arrangement of fibers with a given aspect ratio (i.e. ratio of length to diameter). For this series of samples, computerised simulation (7) estimates the maximum around $V_f = 20\%$. Any attempt to incorporate more fibers in the composite would result in the break of the fibers thus reducing the in-plane thermal conductivity (8). On the other hand, no effect of that maximum on the out-of-plane thermal conductivity was observed. This is most likely to be attributed to the fact that broken fibers could more easily fit between longer fibers and adopt an inclined position with respect to the main faces of the plaques thus increasing the out-of-plane thermal conductivity. The dependence on the fiber concentration can easily be assessed by means of a very simple model. Indeed, an analogy with the prediction of the tensile modulus of chopped fibers filled polymer can be used to fit these linear dependences :

$$K_c = K_m V_m + K_f V_f \epsilon_0 \epsilon_1 \quad (1)$$

Where K is the thermal conductivity, V is the fiber volume fraction and subscripts c , m and f refer respectively to the composite, the matrix and the fibers. ϵ_0 is the efficiency factor accounting for fiber orientation ($0 < \epsilon_0 < 1$) and can be taken as 0.5 for in-plane continuous fibers evenly dispersed. ϵ_1 is the efficiency factor accounting for partial reinforcement ($0 < \epsilon_1 < 1$). Hence, the maximum value for $(\epsilon_0 \epsilon_1)$ that might be expected is less than 0.5.

Least square procedures were applied to the thermal conductivity data and the two lines were drawn in figure 1 and 2 showing that agreement between these results and equation 1 was quite good.

6. CONCLUSION

We have realized a series of plaques of composites in which the chopped fibers were evenly dispersed in planes parallel to the main faces of the plaques. The thermal conductivity was then measured in the direction perpendicular to the axis of the fibers and in a direction parallel to the planes to which the fibers are parallel. Results clearly demonstrated the strong effect of fiber orientation on the thermal conductivity of the composites. When only a threefold increase was observed in the out-of-plane thermal conductivity, values close to that of stainless steel could readily be attained for the in-plane thermal conductivity.

Furthermore, both thermal conductivity dependences on the fiber volume fraction were found to be linear and a very simple model based on an analogy with mechanical properties was proposed.

Finally, we showed the effect of a maximum in the packing of fibers that resulted in the decrease of the in-plane thermal conductivity.

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